

Awareness of Virtual Laboratory Integration for Basic Science Teaching among Pre-service Teachers in Federal University of Education, Kano

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Abstract

This study surveyed the awareness of pre-service science teachers on the nature and use of Virtual Lab; a technology that can be used to augment the practical teaching of science through the use of simulations for immersive learning. The objectives of the study centered on investigating pre-service science teachers' level of familiarity with Virtual Lab, how often they use it and their opinions on its perceived benefits in teaching basic science. The study is inclined to the theory of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which explains how technology users form attitudes and intentions to use a technology. The population of the study consists of B.Ed. science education students from the departments of Biology and Chemistry education in Federal University of Education, Kano. A sample of 108 level 400 students was balloted out of their total population of 220. A structured questionnaire Virtual Lab Knowledge Scale (VLKS) was used to collect data and frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation is used to analyze data. The results show students' familiarity with the existence of Virtual Lab is significant with the mean of 3.40. The mean of 3.97 also shows that they significantly agree to its importance and accessibility. However, the mean of 1.39 shows a significant poor use of virtual lab in teaching and learning. Recommendations made include that Teacher training should give special consideration to the use of trending technology like Virtual Lab and others the teaching. And Pre-service science teachers should be sensitized on how to use accessible gadgets like smart phones to access Virtual Labs and other science teaching technology packages.

Keywords: Virtual Laboratory Integration, Basic Science Teaching, Pre-service Teachers

Introduction

The desire to enhance instruction and increase the chances to achieve science teaching objectives has lead to the innovation of many strategies meant to simplify communication, resourcefulness and other factors necessary for learning to take place. Science teaching is especially known its peculiar demand on various categories of resources; specimens, equipment, models, chemicals among others, which can be capital intensive. Technology Assisted Learning (TAL) has since been a strategy adopted to reduce exhaustive demand on natural resources and increase students' chances to participate in cognitive and physical activities that culminates into learning science concepts. This begins with simulations, using analogies, models, puzzles, animations etc. The advancement of computers and other Instructional Communication Technology (ICT) devices opens the horizon for a better means of involving learners in a seemingly real simulated atmosphere. Science process skills and aspects of its content form the basis of various computer games and puzzles.

Higher advancement in computerization as seen from 1900s lead to the proliferation of more encompassing TAL packages like the internet and web-based technologies enables the development of online Virtual Labs. In the same vein, Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) in the late 1900s and early 2000s expanded the possibilities for immersive and interactive Virtual Labs. As the name suggests, Virtual Lab can be described as a simulated laboratory environment that allows students to conduct experiments and investigations remotely, using digital tools and technologies. The incessant rise in the cost of commodities, services, student's enrollment poor access to quality science education, especially at basic levels in developing countries like Nigeria makes Virtual Labs a remarkable innovation and it is thought that the training of pre-service science teachers should include as its main focus the need to familiarize teacher in training with this digital tool and use them in teaching science.

De Jong et al. (2013) gave the glad tidings that Virtual Lab have emerged as a potential solution to these challenges, offering interactive and immersive learning experience that can enhance student engagement, motivation and learning outcomes. In support of this assertion Kozma (2003) emphasized that Virtual Labs can provide students with access to high-quality laboratory experiences, regardless of their geographical location or economic situation. Kozma (2003) further explained that virtual labs can provide students with access to laboratory experience that may not be available in their local schools. Zhang et al. (2015) supported that Virtual Labs can provide students with the opportunities to conduct experiments and

investigations in a controlled and safe environment, leading to improved learning outcomes. Jong et al. (2013) saw the advantages of Virtual Labs in their ability to improve engagement by providing interactive and immersive learning experience that can enhance student engagement and motivation. Virtual Labs have the potential to improve science education in under-developing countries through enhanced interactions and the creation of a sense of presence and engagement for learners. Research on the understanding of the prospects of Virtual Labs is essential in order to identify effective strategies for employing it in teaching.

Some Virtual Labs that can be used for teaching the components of biology, chemistry, physics, earth science, environmental science and health science in basic science education include: Simulation-based Virtual Labs this was described by De Jong et al. (2013) as labs that use computer simulation to mimic real-world experiments and investigation. Examples include PhET and Open-Source Physics, Remote Controlled Virtual Labs which Corter et al. (2011) described as setting that allows students to remotely control real laboratory equipment in real-time. Examples include LabXchange and Remote Labs, Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality as explained by Freina & Ott (2015), these labs use VR and AR technologies to create immersive and interactive learning experience. They include zSpace and Unimersiv. Shute (2008) highlighted that these labs provide students with interactive and immersive experience to explore and learn about human anatomy and physiology.

As the study focuses on the perception and familiarity of pre-service science teachers on the advancement of technology for augmenting science teaching, it is inclined to the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) theory. This theory was first introduced by Fred Davis in 1989 (Davis 1989) and it explains how technology users form attitudes and intentions to use a technology. Davis inclined the theory to the theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) postulated by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) and aims to explain the factors that influence an individual's decision to accept use a new technology. The theory emphasized that an individuals' decision to use a technology can be influenced by two main factors which are Perceived usefulness that is the degree to which an individual believes that using the technology will improve their performance to achieve desired goals (Davis 1989) and Perceived ease of use; the degree to which the individual believes that using the technology will be free from effort (Davis 1989).

Davis (1989) went further to elaborate that Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) are positively related to Attitude Towards Using (ATU). He also positively linked ATU to Behavioral Intentions (BI) and Actual Use (AU). This theory has gained numerous empirical validations including that of E-commerce of Gefen & Straub (2000) in which he examined the adoption of online shopping and found that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were significant predictors of attitudes towards online shopping which in turn predicted intentions to shop. Another empirical validation to this theory are those in Healthcare, for instance, Holden & Karsh (2010) studies the adoption of Electronic Health Records (EHR) and reported that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were significant predictors of attitude to use EHRs. Liang et al. (2011) investigated the role of trust in the adoption of telemedicine and found that trust was a significant predictor of perceived usefulness, which in turn predicted intentions to use. Later Venkatesh & Davis (2000) incorporated social influence and cognitive instrumental process as additional factors that can influence ATU, BI and AU. Vankatesh & Bala (2008) also included trust, perceived enjoyment and objective usability as more factors that can influence ATU, BI and AU. These studies show the applicability of TAM to various contexts including the use of technology like virtual labs in teaching science.

It is apparent that lack of science teaching resources has been a great impediment to the effective teaching of all the facets of science curriculum. This compounds the inaccessibility to qualitative science education that perpetuates the disparity in science literacy and critical thinking skills between students from developed and under developed countries which hinders the development of skilled and innovative work force necessary for economic growth and enhanced competitive capacity. The advent of Virtual Lab will thus bring a break through to effective science teaching. However, even with the existence of this technology it is evident that many science teachers still resort to rote teaching and use of resources which are insufficient, outdated or poorly improvised. Could it be that pre-service science teachers are not exposed to such new innovations and their lofty benefits? This study thus set to investigate pre-service science teachers' familiarity with Virtual Lab and its prospect in solving problems in science teaching and increasing opportunities for better learning.

Objectives of the Study

1. To investigate pre-service science teachers' level of Awareness with Virtual Lab.
2. To find out how often do pre-service science teachers use Virtual Labs.
3. To investigate pre-service science teachers' opinions on the perceived benefits of using Virtual Lab in teaching basic science

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

1. What is pre-service science teachers' level of Awareness with Virtual Lab?
2. How often do pre-service science teachers use Virtual Labs?
3. What are pre-service science teachers' opinions on the perceived benefits of using Virtual Lab in teaching basic science?

Methodology

The research is a survey study and it employs the use of researcher developed questionnaire to generate data that was used to answer to purported research questions. The main goal of this survey is to investigate the extent to which pre-service science teachers are familiar with the effectiveness of virtual labs in teaching basic science education. The target population for this study consists of B.sc Ed students in Federal College of Education Kano. As at 2023/2024 session levels 300 and 400 B. Sc Ed biology students are 153 and 194 respectively and B. Sc Ed chemistry have 24 and 26 students in the respective levels this makes the total population of the study to be 397 B. Sc Ed students in FCE, Kano. The sampling process was done in two phases. First the researcher selected levels 400 students as being the students that spends the longest time in the teacher training program it was assumed that they are more likely to be more exposed to more teaching experience. Thus, the total of 220 level 400 students was selected. To obtain a manageable figure 50% of the level 400 students' population are randomly sampled from biology using balloting and the 26 level 400 chemistry students are selected, this provides a sample of 108 students employed in the study.

A structured questionnaire titled Virtual Lab Knowledge Scale (VLKS) designed with multiple choice and Likert scale options was used to collect data. The questionnaire has four sections soliciting pre-service science teachers' level of familiarity with Virtual Lab, types of Virtual Labs pre-service science teachers familiar with, how often do pre-service science teachers use Virtual Labs and per-service science teachers' opinions on the perceived benefits of using Virtual Lab in teaching basic science as demanded by the research objectives and questions. The validity of the VLKS was ascertained by experts' reviews. It was given to experts to examine its relevance in gathering data that can be used to answer the research questions and achieve the research objectives. They also checked the adequacy and relevance of the content to the context of Virtual Lab, organization and structure and made necessary amendments.

Results

Research Question 1:

What is pre-service science teachers' level of Awareness with Virtual Lab?

Table 1: Pre-service science teachers' responses on their familiarity with Virtual Lab (frequencies and percentages)

S/N	Questionnaire Items	1	2	3	4	5
Frequencies and percentages						
1	How conversant are you with the term Virtual Labs?	4 (4.93)	6 (7.41)	6 (7.41)	35 (43.21)	30 (37.04)
2	How often is virtual lab used in your teaching or learning experience?	46 (56.79)	34 (41.97)	1 (1.23)	0 (0)	0 (0)
3	Rate your awareness of the appreciable numbers of free, open source Virtual Labs for science teachers and students.	36 (44.44)	22 (27.16)	18 (22.22)	5 (6.17)	0 (0)
4	To what extent did you know that you can download and use Virtual Labs on smart phone	5 (6.17)	10 (12.35)	15 (18.51)	20 (24.69)	31 (31.27)
5	Did you agree that simulations in virtual labs will be far better than resorting to verbal teaching and theory of practical employed in teaching basic science in Nigeria.	0 (0)	4 (4.93)	5 (6.17)	29 (35.80)	43 (53.08)
6	Virtual labs can only be accessed in developed countries	3 (3.70)	5 (6.17)	10 (12.34)	21 (25.92)	42 (51.85)
7	Virtual lab only addressed the curriculum content of advanced countries	5 (6.17)	3 (3.70)	11 (13.58)	20 (24.69)	42 (51.85)

$$\text{Mean} = \mu = \frac{\sum(Xi \times fi)}{N} = 3.40$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fi (Xi - \mu)^2}{N}} = 1.01$$

Table 1 shows the occurrence of the highest frequencies and percentages in pre-service science students' familiarity with virtual lab and its essential features. More than 65% responded to being conversant with the term Virtual Lab, 55.96% are aware that Virtual Labs can be downloaded and used on smart phones. 88% agreed that simulation in virtual lab is better than verbal teaching and theory of practical in teaching basic science in Nigeria. 77.77% are of a strong perception that Virtual labs can only be accessed in developed countries, and 76.54% hold a strong perception that Virtual labs only addressed the curriculum content of advanced countries. It was also gathered that 98.76 reported the seldom use of virtual lab used in teaching or learning experience and 71.6% reported poor employment of virtual lab in teaching or learning experience. The mean of 3.40 suggests a significantly familiarity to virtual labs and the standard deviation of 1.01 indicates moderate variability in responses.

Research Question 2:

How often do pre-service science teachers use Virtual Labs?

Table 2: Pre-service science teachers' responses on how often they use Virtual Lab (frequencies and percentages)

S/N	Type of Virtual Lab	1	2	3	4	5
1	PhET Interactive Simulations	58 (71.60)	16 (19.75)	7 (8.64)	0 (0)	0 (0)
2	Open Source Physics Lab	52 (64.19)	26 (32.09)	3 (3.70)	0 (0)	0 (0)
3	Virtual Labs for Science Experiments	80 (98.76)	1 (0.81)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
4	Virtual Field Trips Lab	81 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
5	Lobster Biology Lab	52 (64.19)	24 (29.63)	5 (6.17)	0 (0)	0 (0)
6	Synthetic Biology Simulations	72 (88.88)	6 (7.41)	3 (3.70)	0 (0)	0 (0)
7	CK-12 simulations	51 (62.96)	28 (34.57)	2 (2.47)	0 (0)	0 (0)
8	Geogebra Mathematics Simulation Lab	81 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Mean= $\mu = \frac{\sum(Xi \times fi)}{N} = 1.39$

Standard Deviation= $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fi (Xi - \mu)^2}{N}} = 0.53$

Table 2 displays the responses of pre-service science teachers on how often they use Virtual Labs in their teaching and learning, including personal studies. It is apparent that largest percentages of them have never employed the use of virtual lab in any capacity. Virtual Fields Lab and Geogebra Mathematics Simulation Lab have 100% never utilization, then Virtual Lab for Science Experiments with 98.76%, Synthetic Biology Simulations 88.88%, and PhET Interactive Simulation 71.60 never utilization percentages. This illustrates a great underutilization of Virtual Labs as a technology developed to foster the effective teaching of science education. The mean of 1.39 indicates a significant low use of the virtual labs presented and the standard deviation of 0.53 also shows low variability in responses.

Research Question 3:

What are pre-service science teachers' opinions on the perceived benefits of using Virtual Lab in teaching basic science?

S/N	Questionnaire Items	1	2	3	4	5
1	Virtual Labs can be accessed and used in teaching basics science even in remote areas	15 (18.52)	20 (24.69)	21 (25.93)	11 (13.58)	14 (17.28)
2	Virtual Labs can give science learners in developing countries the chance to know and use advanced science teaching equipments.	10 (12.35)	14 (17.28)	12 (14.81)	23 (28.40)	21 (25.93)
3	Virtual lab can adequately replace physical labs in teaching basic science in Nigerian	14 (17.28)	10 (12.34)	10 (12.34)	29 (35.80)	21 (25.92)
4	Virtual labs can create avenues for interactive and immersive teaching and learning	10 (12.93)	9 (11.11)	14 (17.28)	20 (24.69)	30 (37.03)
5	Simulations in virtual labs can be so real and beyond the use of ill equipped science corners in Nigerian primary and junior secondary schools	14 (17.28)	14 (17.28)	21 (25.91)	16 (19.75)	14 (17.28)
6	Virtual labs is ideal for countries with limited resources as it can be scaled up or down to accommodate different class size	14 (17.28)	13 (16.05)	13 (16.05)	24 (29.63)	36 (44.44)
7	Virtual labs can save cost and time in teaching practical and theory in basic science teaching	6 (7.41)	5 (6.17)	11 (13.58)	13 (16.05)	44 (54.32)

Table 3:
Pre-

service science teachers' responses on the benefits of Virtual Lab (frequencies and percentages)

$$\text{Mean} = \mu = \frac{\sum(Xi \times fi)}{N} = 3.97$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum fi (Xi - \mu)^2}{N}} = 1.12$$

Table 3 presents the responses of pre-service science teachers on their views on the perceived benefits of Virtual Labs. 70.37% highly agreed that virtual labs can save cost and time in teaching science, 74.07% highly agreed that Virtual lab is ideal for countries with limited resources as it can be scaled up or down to accommodate different class size. 61.72% agreed that Virtual lab can adequately replace physical labs in teaching basic science in Nigerian. Virtual labs can create avenues for interactive and immersive teaching and learning was highly agreed by 61.72%. The results show the attestation of pre-service science teachers to benefits of Virtual Labs in teaching science. The mean of 3.97 suggests a significant agreement to the perceived benefits of virtual and the standard deviation of 1.12 shows moderate variability in responses.

Discussion of Findings

The study shows that students' are aware of the existence of virtual lab and its essential features. They are at least conversant with the term Virtual Lab, and are aware that Virtual Labs are accessible and can be downloaded and used on smart phones. Respondents held the view that simulation in virtual lab is better than verbal teaching and theory of practical in teaching basic science in Nigeria. This aligns with the opinion of De Jong et al. (2013) that Virtual Labs have the potential to improve science education in under-developing countries through enhanced interactions and the creation of a sense of presence and engagement for learners. However, most of them hold a strong perception that Virtual labs can only be accessed in developed countries, and it only addressed the curriculum content of advanced countries. Majority also reported the seldom use of virtual lab used in teaching or learning experience. It is apparent that largest percentages of pre-service science teachers have never employed the use of virtual lab as a technology developed to foster the effective teaching of science education. With regards to the views on the perceived benefits of Virtual Labs majority responses agreed that virtual labs can save cost and time in teaching science, and it is ideal for countries with limited resources. Pre-service science teacher also commended that Virtual lab can adequately replace physical labs in teaching basic science in Nigerian. This buttressed the view of Kozma (2003) that virtual labs can provide students with access to laboratory experience that may not be available in their local schools. The quality of Virtual labs in creating avenues for interactive and immersive teaching and learning was highly acknowledged. The study strongly shows the attestation of pre-service science teachers to benefits of Virtual Labs in teaching science, but poor patronage in teaching and learning.

Pre-service science teachers not using Virtual labs in science teaching could be attributed to pre-service science teachers' poor trust on the benefit of virtual lab in science teaching. This is in line with the opinion of Vankatesh & Bala (2008) that trust, perceived enjoyment and objective usability are factors that can influence ATU, BI and AU. Liang et al. (2011) also

found that trust was a significant predictor of perceived usefulness, which in turn predicted intentions to telemedicine. The most known Virtual Lab to pre-service science teachers is the Lobster Biology Lab, Synthetic Biology Simulations, Open-Source Lab and virtual Field Labs. The overall result depicts a poor pre-service science teachers' familiarity with specific Virtual Labs available for aiding science teaching. This result contradicts the assertion of Davis (1989) on TAM that Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU) are positively related to Attitude towards Using (ATU), because although pre-service science teachers perceived the usefulness of Virtual Labs in science teaching this did not influence them to use it.

Conclusion

Pre-service science teachers are left far behind in the use of Virtual Lab as a new science teaching technology advanced to provide avenue for interactive, immersive teaching in reduced cost and time. The awareness of the existence of virtual lab and its benefits did not influence pre-service teachers' use of the technology in teaching and learning. The major stake holders in Nigerian education; teachers and students are in serious need of sensitization on the need to be abreast with new means or engaging students with an equipped, safe, and accessible technology.

Recommendations

The findings of the study provide the basis for purporting the following recommendations:

1. Teacher training should give special consideration to the use of trending technology like Virtual Lab and others the teaching.
2. Pre-service science teachers should be sensitized on how to use accessible gadgets like smart phones to access Virtual Labs and other science teaching technology packages.
3. Science education curriculum should emphasis on practical development and use of teaching packages especially those on Virtual Labs and related technology.

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